

50th cessed
anniversary
conference 2026
Bergen Norway

Future-ready social science: **Data, policy, and impact**

15-18 June | Conference Programme

Acknowledgement

CESSDA would like to express our sincere thanks to our Service Providers and partners for their continued support and engagement over the past 50 years. We are grateful for the support of the Norwegian Research Council under the Calls for Coordination and Support Activity for this conference. We also wish to extend our thanks to the City of Bergen for hosting the Welcome Reception at Håkonshallen.

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Data and Science Policy: A New Focus

Digital transformation, open science, and artificial intelligence are shaping how research is carried out and its connection with society. From climate change, inequality, to disinformation – as social challenges grow more urgent and complex, the need for trustworthy, interoperable, and policy-relevant social science data has never been greater. In this evolving landscape, social science data archives play a critical role in maximising the benefits of research data while mitigating potential risks, under the principle of “as open as possible and as closed as necessary”.

In 2026, CESSDA, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, celebrates its 50th anniversary. This conference marks its fifth decade of collaboration, innovation, and service to the European social science research community. It brings together its Service Providers and partners, as well as researchers, open science and data experts, policy actors, funding partners, and networks from across Europe and beyond to reflect on its legacy and chart a shared vision for the future.

The four-day conference programme is anchored in CESSDA's strategic pillars (2023–2027) of **Data**, **People**, and **andscape**. The conference is an opportunity for scientific and policy voices to ask bold questions, strengthen synergies, and set the course for a future-ready European Research Area.

Data: Reshaping Social Sciences in a New Era

CESSDA is at the forefront of enhancing metadata and data interoperability. The consortium supports responsible data sharing and governance through community principles such as FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User Focus, Sustainability, and Technology), and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics). In an evolving data ecosystem marked by emerging fields in the social sciences and the rise of artificial intelligence (AI), CESSDA is committed to supporting data-driven social sciences that address real-world challenges and inform evidence-based policymaking.

People: Connecting Communities

People are the foundation of resilient and sustainable research infrastructures. CESSDA continuously connects the human dimension of data, including researchers, data stewards, and engaged citizens, to foster innovation and collaboration. CESSDA offers a wide range of tools and services to support citizen science and train early-career researchers. Beyond the Social Science and Humanities (SSH) community, CESSDA fosters inclusive dialogue across disciplines at national, European, and global levels.

Landscape: Shaping the Future of the European Research Area

CESSDA is a trusted and long-standing actor in the European Research Area in developing metadata and data standards (e.g., CoreTrustSeal and the Data Documentation Initiative). The consortium contributes to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the advancement of Sustainable Development Goals through participation in diverse European Union-funded projects. It is committed to collaborating with other European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and international partners, namely the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA) and the WorldFAIR project, to address societal challenges and shape a sustainable future.

By organising this conference, CESSDA aims to foster partnerships between data experts and relevant stakeholders to advance science policy. The conference discussions will contribute to shaping a future-ready landscape – one where policy and science are interconnected, and cross-border collaborations catalyse scientific excellence.

“Join us to celebrate five decades of impact and help define the future of social science data. Let’s work together to ensure that research infrastructures remain inclusive, resilient, and ready for our common future”

Dr. Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch, CESSDA ERIC Executive Director.

Learn about our
strategy

CESSDA and its 22 Service Providers

CESSDA, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives, was founded in 1976 as an informal umbrella organisation for national social science data archives in Europe. It has since evolved into a legal entity, now an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium), that promotes high-quality and trusted social science research. CESSDA, together with its Service Providers (SPs) (i.e., national social science data archives) from 22 member countries, offer integrated and sustainable data services by connecting national data archives across Europe.

The 22 member countries dedicate tremendous time and effort to leverage Open Science practices, addressing the needs of data users, and tracking their impact and progress regularly. They are **Austria** (AUSSDA), **Belgium** (SODHA), **Croatia** (CROSSDA), **Czechia** (ČSDA), **Finland** (FSD), **France** (Progedo), **Germany** (GESIS), **Greece** (SoDaNet), **Hungary** (TÁRKI), **Iceland** (DATICE), **Ireland** (ISSDA), **Italy** (DASSI), **Lithuania** (LiDA), the **Netherlands** (DANS), **North Macedonia** (MK DASS), **Norway** (Sikt), **Portugal** (APIS), **Slovakia** (SASD), **Slovenia** (ADP), **Sweden** (SND), **Switzerland** (FORS), and the **United Kingdom** (UKDS).

The 22 member countries collaborate closely with CESSDA's 12 partner countries to enable the research community to conduct high-quality social science research. The partner countries are **Albania** (ADAS), **Bosnia and Herzegovina** (Data Archive for Social Sciences), **Bulgaria** (The National Data Service), **Estonia** (University of Tartu Library), **Kosovo** (KSSDC), **Latvia** (RSU), **Luxembourg** (LISER), **Montenegro** (MSSDA), **Poland** (PADS), **Romania** (RODA), **Serbia** (DCS), and **Ukraine** (Kyiv archive).

CESSDA, as a Landmark of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), illustrates its scientific relevance and credibility within the European Research Area. CESSDA supports researchers in discovering and assessing over

37K datasets in national languages, through tools such as the European Language Social Science Thesaurus, Vocabulary Service, and Data Catalogue. CESSDA provides extensive training to foster the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) for research data. CESSDA contributes to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the advancement of Sustainable Development Goals through participation in diverse European Union-funded projects.

In 2026, CESSDA celebrates its 50th anniversary. The CESSDA community seeks to champion this legacy and continue to increase the scientific excellence and efficacy of social science research.

Abbreviation	Full Service Providers' names
ADP	Social Science Data Archives
APIS	Portuguese Social Information Archive
AUSSDA	Austrian Social Science Data Archive
CROSSDA	Croatian Social Science Data Archive
ČSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DASSI	Data Archive for Social Sciences in Italy
DATICE	Icelandic Social Science Data Service
FORS	Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
GESIS	GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
ISSDA	Irish Social Science Data Archive
LiDA	Lithuanian Data Archive for Humanities and Social Sciences
MK DASSI	Social Science Data Archive of North Macedonia
Progedo	Progedo Research Infrastructure
SASD	Slovak Archive of Social Data
Sikt	Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research
SND	Swedish National Data Service
SoDaNet	Greek Research Infrastructure for the Social Sciences
SODHA	Social Sciences and Digital Humanities Archive
TÁRKI	Tárki Social Science Data Archive
UKDS	UK Data Service

CESSDA Tools and Services

Technology underpins CESSDA's technical infrastructure. It provides a stable and up-to-date foundation for CESSDA's tools and services to make it easy to deposit and access data.

Data Catalogue

A one-stop shop for searching and discovering social science data. It contains descriptions (metadata) of more than 40,000 studies held by CESSDA's Service Providers across Europe.

European Language Social Science Thesaurus

A thesaurus consisting of over 3,300 concepts in social sciences available in 15 languages. It enhances access to data resources independent of domain or language.

Vocabulary Service

Enables users to discover, browse, and download controlled vocabularies in 13 languages. Downloading is possible in SKOS, HTML and PDF formats in the selected languages.

European Question Bank

A survey question bank that integrates and displays metadata from several European data archives. It enables users to search, browse, compare, and download multilingual survey questions and study-related metadata.

Resource Directory

A curated inventory of resources to support the development of services and features in data archives. The resources include reports, training materials, and technical documentation.

Metadata Validator

Validates Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) metadata records used by CESSDA's tools and services against a given DDI Profile.

Data Management Expert Guide

Guides researchers and data professionals to make research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Available in PDF and interactive game versions.

Data Archiving Guide

Provides a general understanding of the full range of activities a data repository performs. Learn what a data archive is, what it does, and why data archives play an important role in the scientific infrastructure.

Data Citation Guide

Offers practical recommendations to key stakeholders to properly cite data. Learn why data citation matters, what a citation should include, and how best practices can be applied across the research landscape.

Learn more about our
impact

CESSDA Working Groups

The CESSDA Working Groups were established to bring together experts to collaborate on tasks and develop recommendations supporting its strategic pillars for the period from 2023 to 2027– **Data, People, and Landscape**.

The CESSDA workshops on Days 1 and 2 are kindly organised by the Working Group leaders.

Trust and Landscape

The Trust and Landscape Working Group monitors developments in open data and research data management. It offers strategic recommendations supporting the community principles for data management and stewardship (e.g., FAIR) and strengthens partnerships with key stakeholders in Europe (e.g., EOSC). It supports Service Providers in upholding high standards for trust and long-term data preservation through certifications such as CoreTrustSeal.

Interoperability Coordination

The Interoperability Coordination Working Group oversees the development, maintenance, harmonisation, and promotion of CESSDA tools and services. It supports Service Providers in implementing and maintaining international metadata standards. It offers technical solutions to ensure CESSDA tools and services are transparent, trustworthy, and accessible to both humans and machines.

Artificial Intelligence

The Artificial Intelligence Working Group advances innovation, ethical practices, and practical application of AI in repository operations. It supports Service Providers in assessing and piloting AI-driven solutions to improve the workflow of repository operations (e.g., data curation) and to better address user needs. It develops good practices for the responsible use of AI. It facilitates knowledge sharing, monitors emerging trends in AI, and contributes to shaping CESSDA's strategic approach to AI adoption.

Sensitive Data Access

The Sensitive Data Access Working Group focuses on ensuring that access to sensitive research data is properly managed and secured. Together with CESSDA Service Providers, it promotes best practices and pilots solutions for information security, data anonymisation, access control, and risk mitigation for safe data sharing and access.

Data Citation

The Data Citation Working Group promotes interoperable and consistent data citation practices to encourage data discovery and reuse. It develops practical recommendations for key stakeholders beyond the CESSDA community, including researchers, publishers, and funding entities. It supports Service Providers in fostering a culture of data citation.

CESSDA Dataverse

Dataverse is an open-source web-based application to share, preserve, cite, explore, and analyse research data. The CESSDA Dataverse Working Group serves as a knowledge-sharing hub among Service Providers using the Dataverse software for data archiving and long-term preservation. It coordinates further development of the platform based on Service Providers' needs, such as multilingual metadata, integration of standardised terms, and linking with the Research Organisation Registry (ROR).

The Objectives of the Conference

The conference marks the 50th anniversary of CESSDA. It celebrates its impact on open science and open data in the European Research Area and beyond. It brings together CESSDA Service Providers, researchers, policy actors, partner organisations, and international networks to share knowledge, showcase achievements, and address the evolving landscape of research and innovation.

The conference is framed around CESSDA's 2023-2027 vision and its strategic pillars of **Data**, **People**, and **Landscape**. The conference presents an opportunity to explore how data services, research infrastructures, and collaborations can evolve to meet the needs of data users in an era of AI and digital transformation. It aims to strengthen CESSDA's role as a landmark in the European Research Area and to foster meaningful dialogue across disciplines, institutions, and borders.

The conference is both a celebration and a call to action: to build a more resilient, inclusive, and future-ready European research data ecosystem.

Key Questions the Conference Aims to Address

- How can CESSDA and its Service Providers better support evidence-based policymaking through open, trustworthy, and interoperable data services?
- How do we engage the next generation of researchers and data professionals in building sustainable, FAIR, and trustworthy data ecosystems?
- What models of collaboration (across research infrastructures, funding partners, and international networks) are needed to shape the future of the European Research Area?
- What does it mean to be “future-ready” as a research infrastructure? What concrete steps must we take to lead the way forward?

Conference Overview

Check in

All participants are kindly asked to check in by scanning a QR code once, so we can accurately track daily attendance.

Day 1 (June 15): CESSDA Workshops

Location: Kulturhuset, Galeriet, 3rd floor

Day 1 focuses on strengthening the development of CESSDA's services and collaborations. The workshops, kindly organised by Working Group leaders, discuss interoperability within the European Research Area, trust practices, and approaches to sensitive data access. The workshops also offer guidance for multilingual Dataverse services and data citation.

Day 2 (June 16): CESSDA Workshops

Location: Kulturhuset, Galeriet, 3rd floor

Day 2 explores the role of artificial intelligence in shaping the future of CESSDA services and practices. The AI and Interoperability Working Groups bring together external speakers to examine real-world applications of AI for enriching metadata and enabling automated workflows, while addressing ethical and regulatory considerations. The workshop discussions will help inform a strategic and responsible path for AI adoption within CESSDA.

Day 3 (June 17): Looking back to look forward

Location: Media City Bergen, Atlantis Auditorium, lower level

Day 3 reflects on the evolution of the European Research Area, FAIR data and responsible AI, and strategies for building a skilled workforce for open science. The sessions provide key insights and lessons to guide the future of research infrastructures. The keynote celebrates CESSDA's 50 years of impact on societal progress and trust in data.

Day 4 (June 18): Innovate, collaborate, and act

Location: Media City Bergen, Atlantis Auditorium, lower level

Day 4 focuses on innovation, collaboration, and action. The sessions explore how social science data, AI, and emerging research approaches can address societal challenges. The sessions also highlight evolving user needs, citizen science, and skill development. The plenary reflects on four days of discussion and proposes next steps for our common future.

Social events

Welcome reception on Day 2 at 18:30 at **Håkonshallen, Bergenshus 10, 5003 Bergen.**

Conference dinner on Day 4 at 19:00 at **Frescohallen, Vågsallmenningen 1, 5014 Bergen.**

Day 1: CESSDA Workshops

WORKSHOP 1: INTEROPERABILITY ECOSYSTEM

Back to Basics

Speakers: Darren Bell (UKDS) and Matthew Morris (CESSDA ERIC)

Within the European Research Area (ERA), CESSDA, EOSC, DDI, and W3C standards are interlinked and play an important role in data repositories. This workshop uses plain, non-technical language to introduce:

- How do CESSDA, EOSC, SSHOC, and the DDI Alliance fit together in the ERA?
- What do “interoperability” and “federation” mean for data repositories of different sizes, and why does it matter for researchers and Service Providers?
- How do core tools and standards (e.g., CDC, ELSST, Dataverse, Colectica, RDF, Croissant, DCAT, etc.) interact to support research infrastructures?

WORKSHOP 2: TRUST & LANDSCAPE

CoreTrustSeal Support: CESSDA Common Evidence

Speakers: Mari Kleemola (FSD), Hervé L'Hours (UKDS), Maaike Verburg (DANS), and Ami Saji (Progedo)

CESSDA's common resources (e.g., guidance, standards, policies) can help illustrate commitments to community principles (e.g., FAIR, TRUST, and CARE) more coherently. These common resources can be used as evidence when applying CoreTrustSeal Certification. This workshop discusses:

- What are the lessons learned from applying for CoreTrustSeal?
- How can CESSDA Common Evidence support CoreTrustSeal applications?
- How can the FIDELIS Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM) be used to support the certification process?
- How can the CESSDA CoreTrustSeal support be improved?

WORKSHOP 3: SENSITIVE DATA ACCESS

Advancing Access to Sensitive Data within CESSDA

Speakers Brian Kleiner (FORS) and Deborah Wiltshire (GESIS)

Strengthening coordination around sensitive data access can enable CESSDA to build Trusted Research Environments that support secure data sharing and federated analysis. Drawing from a community-wide survey, this workshop explores:

- What needs and challenges does CESSDA face in managing sensitive data and emerging data types, and where is coordination most beneficial?
- Which practices, solutions, and technical models show the greatest promise for enabling secure data sharing and analysis of sensitive data?

WORKSHOP 4: CESSDA DATAVERSE

Multilingual Dataverse Services: Models, Solutions, and Workarounds

Speakers Lars Kaczmirek (AUSSDA) and Lorenz Makula (AUSSDA)

Implementing multilingual Dataverse services requires careful consideration of trade-offs between scalability, sustainability, maintainability, and upgrade safety. This workshop explores key questions to support informed decision-making:

- What architectural models (e.g., single instance with multilingual user interface and metadata vs. scoped collections) best support scalable and maintainable multilingual services?
- What practical solutions and workarounds can support multilingual metadata and interfaces while ensuring upgrade safety and operational reliability?
- How can these approaches best serve our diverse user communities?

WORKSHOP 5: DATA CITATION

Data Citation and Tracking: Practical Solutions for CESSDA

Speakers Tuomas J. Alaterä (FSD), André Jernung (SND), Farah Karim (GESIS), Lisa Tveit Sandberg (Sikt)

Consistent data citation practices are essential for recognising data as a valuable research output, enhancing data discovery, and facilitating data tracking. This workshop offers practical guidance on applying the CESSDA Data Citation Guide and discusses:

- How can CESSDA align institutional policies, workflows, and metadata with the Guide?
- How can the Guide be used to engage new communities and promote data citation practices?
- What approaches and technical solutions can improve the tracking of data citation and reuse?

Day 1, Monday 15 June

Kulturhuset, Galeriet, 3rd floor

8:45–9:00	Registration	
9:00–9:30	Opening Session	
9:30–10:30	WORKSHOP 1: Interoperability Ecosystem Back to Basics	SPEAKERS Darren Bell , UKDS, United Kingdom Matthew Morris , CESSDA ERIC
10:30–11:00	Tea/coffee break	
11:00–12:30	WORKSHOP 2: Trust & Landscape CoreTrustSeal Support: CESSDA Common Evidence	SPEAKERS Mari Kleemola , FSD, Finland Hervé L'Hours , UK Data Service, United Kingdom Maaïke Verburg , DANS, Netherlands Ami Saji , Progedo, France
12:30–13:30	Lunch	
13:30–14:30	WORKSHOP 3: Sensitive Data Access Advancing Access to Sensitive Data within CESSDA	SPEAKERS Brian Kleiner , FORS, Switzerland Deborah Wiltshire , GESIS, Germany
14:30–15:30	WORKSHOP 4: CESSDA Dataverse Multilingual Dataverse Services: Models, Solutions, and Workarounds	SPEAKERS Lars Kaczmirek , AUSSDA, Austria Lorenz Makula , University of Vienna, Austria
15:30–16:00	Tea/coffee break	

Day 1, Monday 15 June

Kulturhuset, Galeriet, 3rd floor

16:00–17:00

WORKSHOP 5: Data Citation

Data Citation
and Tracking:
Practical
Solutions for
CESSDA

SPEAKERS

Tuomas J. Alaterä, FSD, Finland

André Jernung, SND, Sweden

Farah Karim, GESIS, Germany

Lisa Tveit Sandberg, Sikt, Norway

Programme subject to change. Please visit the event page for the latest updates.

Day 2: CESSDA Workshops

WORKSHOP 6: AI Today

Real-world Implications in CESSDA

Speakers: Darren Bell (UKDS), Benjamin Beuster (Sikt), Bojana Tasic (FORS), and Slava Tykhonov (CODATA)

Artificial intelligence offers unprecedented opportunities to strengthen interoperability across CESSDA by generating and enriching metadata at scale, improving metadata and data quality, improving multilingual consistency, and enabling more automated workflows to support data users. The AI and Interoperability Working Groups bring together external speakers to explore:

- Which practical standards or frameworks (e.g. CroissantML) are CESSDA adopting to make data “AI-ready” while safeguarding FAIR principles?
- How can AI-driven metadata enhancements and quality assessments improve the interoperability of metadata across CESSDA?
- What ethical and regulatory safeguards are needed to ensure the responsible use of AI within repositories?

WORKSHOP 7: AI Tomorrow

Mapping Out an AI Future for CESSDA

Speakers: Darren Bell (UKDS), Benjamin Beuster (Sikt), and Bojana Tasic (FORS)

AI is demanding that we rapidly reassess our traditional understanding of repository practice and the types of services that could be delivered. The AI and Interoperability Working Groups co-organise this hands-on session focusing on technology, governance, and skills.

Attendees will be asked to choose one of these three topic areas and participate in a series of interactive exercises and discussions that will provide valuable input into shaping future AI adoption within CESSDA.

Day 2, Tuesday 16 June

Kulturhuset, Galeriet, 3rd floor

9:00–12:30	26th Service Provider Forum (SPF)	SPF delegates
12:30–13:30	Lunch	
13:30–15:00	WORKSHOP 6: AI Today Real-World Implementations in CESSDA	SPEAKERS Darren Bell , UKDS, United Kingdom Benjamin Beuster , Sikt, Norway Bojana Tasic , FORS, Switzerland Slava Tykhonov , CODATA
15:00–15:30	Tea/coffee break	
15:30–16:30	WORKSHOP 7: AI Tomorrow Mapping Out an AI Future for CESSDA	SPEAKERS Darren Bell , UKDS, United Kingdom Benjamin Beuster , Sikt, Norway Bojana Tasic , FORS, Switzerland
16:30–17:30	CLOSING/ NEXT STEPS	SPEAKERS CESSDA Main Office
18:30–19:30	WELCOME RECEPTION Håkonshallen	

Programme subject to change. Please visit the event page for the latest updates.

Day 3: Looking Back to Look Ahead

SESSION 1 (S1): LANDSCAPE

Shaping the European Research Area

Strategic partnership and policy alignment are crucial for building an inclusive and competitive European Research Area (ERA). This session introduces:

- How has the ERA evolved over the past decades, and what major milestones have shaped its development?
- What are the barriers and enablers to effective cross-border and interdisciplinary collaboration?
- How to make the ERA future-ready?

SESSION 2 (S2): DATA

FAIR, TRUST, and CARE in the Data Ecosystem for AI

Standards and policy frameworks must evolve to support open data practices and responsible AI in social science research. This session explores:

- How can research infrastructures strengthen alignment with global data standards, as well as national policies and roadmaps?
- How do FAIR principles remain relevant in an AI-driven landscape, and what are the key risks and opportunities?
- How can we ensure transparency and trust as data systems become more automated and complex?

SESSION 3 (S3): PEOPLE

Skills for Open Science: From National Priorities to Global Collaboration

Training researchers and data experts is crucial for advancing FAIR and open science in Europe and beyond. This session discusses:

- How are national priorities shaping training for open science? What shared approaches are needed in Europe and beyond?
- How can competence centres and other actors collaborate to avoid fragmentation in skills development?

KEYNOTE 1

Social Science Data for Societal Change

To celebrate CESSDA's 50th anniversary, this keynote reflects on the role of open science, the FAIR principles, and high-quality social science data in accelerating societal progress. Taking the Norwegian experience as a starting point and drawing on perspectives from both research practice and statistical infrastructure, it explores how sustained work on data documentation, standardization, and accessibility has expanded the scope for research and policy, and how ongoing digitalization is opening new opportunities while raising fundamental questions of privacy, trust, and social license.

Day 3, Wednesday 17 June

Media City Bergen, Atlantis Auditorium, lower level

08:30-08:45	Registration	
8:45-9:30	OPENING SESSION	<p>CHAIR Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch, Executive Director, CESSDA ERIC</p> <p>SPEAKERS</p> <p>Live Haaland, Director, Department for Higher Education, Research and International Affairs, Ministry of Education and Research, Norway</p> <p>Benedicte Løseth, Executive Director for Research System and Internationalisation, Research Council of Norway</p> <p>Bjørn Henrichsen, Former President, CESSDA ERIC</p> <p>Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy, Chair of CESSDA General Assembly & Deputy Head, Ministry of Women, Research and Science, Austria</p> <p>RAPPORTEUR Johan Van Der Eycken, Director of Digital Archiving Service, SODHA, Belgium</p>
9:30-11:00	S1: LANDSCAPE Shaping the European Research Area	<p>CHAIR José Luis Martínez Peña, ESFRI Forum</p> <p>PANELLISTS</p> <p>Eija Juurola, ACTRIS ERIC</p> <p>Klaus Tochtermann, EOSC/ZBW, Germany</p> <p>Sally Chambers, DARIAH ERIC</p> <p>Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch, CESSDA ERIC</p> <p>DISCUSSANT Michael Arentoft, European Commission</p> <p>RAPPORTEUR Olja Toljagic, Research Council of Norway</p>
11:00-11:30	Tea/coffee break	

Day 3, Wednesday 17 June

Media City Bergen, Atlantis Auditorium, lower level

11:30–13:00	S2: DATA FAIR, TRUST, and CARE in the Data Ecosystem for AI	CHAIR Ingrid Dillo , DANS, Netherlands PANELLISTS Darren Bell , UKDS, United Kingdom Tiziana Ferrari , EGI Mari Kleemola , FSD, Finland Bojana Tasic , FORS, Switzerland DISCUSSANT Simon Hodson , CODATA RAPPORTEUR Marijana Glavica , CROSSDA, Croatia
13:00–14:30	Lunch	
14:30–16:00	S3: PEOPLE Skills for Open Science: From National Priorities to Global Collaboration	CHAIR Steven McEachern , UKDS, United Kingdom PANELLISTS Darja Fišer , CLARIN ERIC Hilary Hanahoe , RDA Eva Stensköld , SND, Sweden Erik Øiolf Sørensen , NHH, Norway DISCUSSANT Georg Lutz , FORS, Switzerland RAPPORTEUR Maja Dolinar , ADP, Slovenia
16:00–16:30	Tea/coffee break	
16:30–17:15	KEYNOTE Session 1	CHAIR Helena Laaksonen , FSD, Finland KEYNOTE Linda Nøstbakken , Statistics Norway, Norway RAPPORTEUR Miloslav Bahna , SASD, Slovakia

Programme subject to change. Please visit the event page for the latest updates.

Day 4: Innovate, Collaborate, and Act

SESSION 1 (S1): LANDSCAPE

Future-ready Together: Bridging Research and Policy

Research infrastructures must take a proactive role in leveraging open, trustworthy, and interoperable data to strengthen policy dialogue and coordination. This session explores:

- How can social science data and research be used to anticipate and respond to future societal challenges?
- Which reforms (e.g., policy, institutional governance, culture) are necessary to harness data for sustainable development?
- What does it mean to be “future-ready” at the intersection of data, research, and science policy?

This session brings together perspectives from research infrastructures, data archives, and policy-oriented initiatives to discuss the shared responsibility of enabling high-quality, transparent, and reusable data.

SESSION 2 (S2): DATA

New Developments in Social Science: A Snapshot

New approaches to data, analysis, and collaboration would be needed to address evolving real-world challenges. This session explores:

- How can social science adapt its data practices to remain relevant in the era of AI and digital transformation?
- What are the ethical and technical challenges of using non-traditional data sources? How can researchers navigate these complexities?
- How can research infrastructures better support researchers working on emerging research topics?

SESSION 3 (S3): PEOPLE

Re-imagine Research: Evolving with Society and Data

AI and technologies are rapidly transforming scientific research processes and user needs. This session explores:

- How are user needs evolving with rapid technological change?
- How can research infrastructures stay relevant and “future-ready”?

KEYNOTE 2

Our Common Future

This keynote reflects the challenges to research and the research infrastructure landscape as AI shapes research and decision-making. The talk addresses how social science data and research infrastructures shall evolve to remain a foundation for trust and innovation.

Day 4, Thursday 18 June

Media City Bergen, Atlantis Auditorium, lower level

9:00–9:15	OPENING SESSION	CHAIR Arlene Healy , ISSDA, Ireland SPEAKER Richard Welpton , ESRC UKRI, United Kingdom
9:15–10:45	S1: LANDSCAPE Future-ready Together: Bridging Research and Policy	CHAIR Dimitra Kondyli , SoDaNet, Greece PANELLISTS Rory Fitzgerald , European Social Survey, United Kingdom Matthew Gray , Australian National University, Australia Hilde Orten , Sikt, Norway Brett Powell , Roper Center, United States DISCUSSANT Carthage Smith , OECD RAPPORTEUR Oлга Zhmurko , ČSDA, Czechia
10:45–11:15	Tea/coffee break	
11:15–12:45	S2: DATA New Developments in Social Science: A Snapshot	CHAIR Nicolas Sauger , Progedo, France PANELLISTS Marta Curto , Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain Catalina Franco , Centre for Applied Research (SNF) and FAIR at NHH Norwegian School of Economics, Norway Pei-Shan Liao , Academia Sinica, Republic of China (Taiwan) Katrin Weller , GESIS, Germany DISCUSSANT Audronė Telešienė , Kaunas University of Technology/LiDA, Lithuania RAPPORTEUR Eiríkur Stephensen , University of Iceland/DATICE, Iceland
12:45–14:00	Lunch	

Day 4, Thursday 18 June

Media City Bergen, Atlantis Auditorium, lower level

14:00–15:30	S3: PEOPLE Re-imagine Research: Evolving with Society and Data	CHAIR Christof Wolf , GESIS, Germany PANELLISTS Seokho Kim , Seoul National University, South Korea Yasuyuki Minamiyama , Institute of Social Science, University of Tokyo, Japan Javier Terán , United Nations OCHA Lynn Woolfrey , University of Cape Town, DataFirst, South Africa DISCUSSANT Jeannette Jackson , ICPSR, University of Michigan, United States RAPPORTEUR Sonia Stefanizzi , DASSI - University of Milan-Bicocca, Italy
15:30–16:00	Tea/coffee break	
16:00–16:45	KEYNOTE SESSION 2	CHAIR Vigdis Namtvedt Kvalheim , Sikt, Norway KEYNOTE Barbara Wasson , University of Bergen, Norway RAPPORTEUR Yana Leontiyeva , ČSDA, Czechia
16:45–17:00	CLOSING SESSION	Wrap-up, looking forward, and farewell SPEAKERS Vigdis Namtvedt Kvalheim , Sikt, Norway Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch , CESSDA ERIC
19:00–22:00	CONFERENCE DINNER Frescohallen (Vågsallmenningen 1)	

Programme subject to change. Please visit the event page for the latest updates.

Speakers Featured on Days 3 and 4

<p>Miloslav Bahna Director SASD, Slovakia</p>	
<p>Sally Chambers Director DARIAH ERIC</p>	
<p>Ingrid Dillo Senior Advisor DANS, Netherlands</p>	
<p>Tiziana Ferrari Director EGI Foundation</p>	
<p>Rory Fitzgerald Professor of Practice in Survey Research European Social Survey, United Kingdom</p>	
<p>Marijana Glavica Acting Head CROSSDA, Croatia</p>	
<p>Live Haaland Director, Department for Higher Education, Research and International Affairs Ministry of Education and Research, Norway</p>	

<p>Arlene Healy Director of Collections and Digital Services ISSDA, Ireland</p>	
<p>Simon Hodson Executive Director CODATA</p>	
<p>Eija Juurola Director General ACTRIS ERIC</p>	
<p>Mari Kleemola Development Manager FSD, Finland</p>	
<p>Helena Laaksonen Director FSD, Finland</p>	
<p>Pei-shan Liao Research Fellow Academia Sinica, Republic of China (Taiwan)</p>	
<p>Benedicte Løseth Executive Director for Research System and Internationalisation Research Council of Norway</p>	
<p>Yasuyuki Minamiyama Associate Professor Institute of Social Science, University of Tokyo, Japan</p>	
<p>Linda Nøstbakken Research Director Statistics Norway</p>	
<p>José Luis Martínez Peña Research Professor ESFRI Forum</p>	

<p>Matthias Reiter-Pázmány Chair of CESSDA General Assembly & Deputy Head Federal Ministry of Women, Science and Research, Austria</p>	
<p>Carthage Smith Senior Policy Analyst OECD</p>	
<p>Eva Stensköld Director SND, Sweden</p>	
<p>Erik Øiof Sørensen Professor of Economics NHH, Norway</p>	
<p>Audronė Telešienė Professor & Head of LiDA LiDA/Kaunas University of Technology, Lithuania</p>	
<p>Klaus Tochtermann Director & President EOSC/ZBW, Germany</p>	
<p>Johan Van Der Eycken Director of Digital Archiving Service SODHA, Belgium</p>	
<p>Katrin Weller Department Head of Data Services for the Social Sciences GESIS, Germany</p>	

<p>Christof Wolf President GESIS, Germany</p>	
<p>Lynn Woolfrey Head of Data Services University of Cape Town/ DataFirst, South Africa</p>	
<p>Olga Zhmurko Researcher ČSDA, Czechia</p>	

Organisers

The Conference is made possible through the hard work of the following organisers, as well as the administrative and coordination support provided by the CESSDA Main Office team.

<p>Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch Executive Director CESSDA ERIC</p>	
<p>Helena Laaksonen Director FSD, Finland</p>	
<p>Olivier Y. Rouquette Team Lead GESIS, Germany</p>	

Practical Information

About Bergen

Bergen is the second-largest city in Norway. Located on Norway's west coast between the Seven Mountains, the city is a UNESCO World Heritage City and a European City of Culture. The city offers a wide variety of nature and cultural experiences year-round, as long as you don't mind a little rain. Bergen has something for everyone – whether you want to see the fjords, hike the mountains, experience live music, or explore the historic sights downtown.

Mountains and fjords

For the best views in Bergen, you can find them at one of Bergen's seven mountains. You can hike or take the Fløibanen funicular to Fløyen. Alternatively, you can hike or take the cable car to Ulriken, the city's highest peak of 643 meters. For the spectacular plunging fjords, there are daily cruises leaving from the city centre to the Hardangerfjord and Sognefjord.

Museums and historic sights

Bergen is a city full of history and tradition – once a major trading port and now a vibrant cultural hub in Northern Europe. It has a wide range of museums and a lively music scene. Some highlights include:

Bryggen

Bryggen is a UNESCO World Heritage site. It is the remains of an old port settlement and one of the most famous medieval urban areas in Norway.

Håkon's Hall (Håkonshallen)

Håkonshallen is the main building of Norway's first castle. It is older than 760 years old. It was built between 1247 and 1261 by King Håkon Håkonsson as a royal residence and feasting hall.

Bergen Natural History Museum

Experience exciting exhibitions within archaeology, anthropology and cultural history. The museum garden is a botanical gem in the centre of Bergen.

KODE Art and Music Museum

KODE is one of the largest museums for art, crafts, design, and music in the Nordic region. It offers classical and contemporary exhibitions.

Food

Want to eat well? Then eat like a local! In 2015, Bergen earned the UNESCO title, “City of Gastronomy”. From hidden gems to famous restaurants, here are some of our personal recommendations while you’re in Bergen:

Chérie – Skostredet Brasserie

Tucked away in Bergen’s backstreets, Chérie mixes local delicacies with an international twist.

Bryggeriet Restaurant

With a view of Bryggen and the fjord, Bryggeriet is a perfect place to enjoy traditional local cuisine.

Skyskraperen Restaurant – Mount Ulriken Restaurant

Skyskraperen is situated on the top of the city mountain, Ulriken. It offers a unique dining experience with a spectacular view of the city.

Recommended apps

The Norwegian society is highly digital. You may find these apps helpful during your stay:

Skyss

Skyss is the app for all public transport (buses and light rail) in the city. You can purchase single tickets or period tickets that last for 24 hours or 7 days. The light rail can take you from the airport to the city centre in 50 minutes.

07000 Taxi

Need to get somewhere in a hurry? The 07000 Taxi app is the fastest and easiest way to book a taxi in Bergen.

About the Workshop Venue

Kulturhuset is Norway's most active and enriching cultural centre. It is located at Vaskerelven 8, 5014 Bergen. The closest Bybanen light rail stop is Byparken.

Galleriet is located on the 3rd floor.

To access Wifi:

SSID: KhiB Guest

Password: KulturBergen

About the Conference Venue

Media City Bergen is a leading international hub for media and technology innovation. It is located at Lars Hilles gate 30, 5008 Bergen. The closest Bybanen light rail stop is Nygård.

There are two main entrances. They are located at Lars Hilles gate 30 and at Odd Frantzens plass 5. Both entrances lead directly into the Atrium.

The Atlantis Auditorium is located on the lower level of the Atrium.

To access Wifi:

SSID: MCB Guest

Connect your device and follow the on-screen instructions.

Map

Welcome reception on Day 2 at 18:00 at Håkonshallen, Bergenhus 10, 5003 Bergen.

Conference dinner on Day 4 at 19:00 at Frescohallen, Vågsallmenningen 1, 5014 Bergen.

Days 1 and 2 at Kulturhuset, Vaskerelven 8, 5014 Bergen.

Days 3 and 4 at Media City Bergen, Lars Hilles gate 30, 5008 Bergen.

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anniversary
conference 2026

15-18 June Bergen Norway

